

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF THE SANITARY CONDITIONS OF DOMESTIC AND INDUSTRIAL WASTEWATER IN TASHKENT CITY AND REGION

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Abstract. *The article provides information on the primary sanitary and hygienic conditions of more than 7 samples: (domestic, industrial wastewater, spring and technical water, etc.), taken from various water samples of Tashkent and the region. Various types of microorganisms have been identified, an initial assessment of their sanitary condition and recommendations for their cleaning are provided.*

Keywords: *wastewater, domestic water, microbiological landscape, sanitary and hygienic condition, bacteria, fungi, actinomycetes, pathogens, condition, cleaning recommendations.*

INTRODUCTION

At present time the issues of optimal and efficient use of water resources in the Republic of Uzbekistan are of great importance. Measures are being developed to eliminate the harmful effects of water. The rational use of local water resources and their protection from pollution remain in the spotlight. Solving these issues is essential for ushering in a new and significant phase in the development of both water management and agriculture.

Nowadays, great attention is being paid to preventing the pollution of water bodies. Wastewater from domestic and industrial enterprises is treated in specific facilities before being discharged back into water bodies. However, even after treatment, these waters can still pollute natural water bodies to some extent. In recent years, several government resolutions have been adopted, mainly aimed at improving the sanitary conditions of water bodies. The rapid development of industrial and agricultural enterprises is one of the main factors contributing to water pollution by wastewater.

Discharging large volumes of wastewater into water bodies while maintaining their cleanliness is a critical task for the national economy. Therefore, selecting the proper method for treating wastewater ensures that the discharged water complies with sanitary standards. Wastewater contains various pollutants, and the presence of organic substances in particular creates favorable conditions for the growth of bacteria. Thus, in the treatment of wastewater, one of the key priorities is the removal and neutralization of these pollutants, especially organic matter [1].

The growing demand for the treatment of wastewater generated from the daily needs of the population of Tashkent city, along with the application of modern technological methods in wastewater treatment, necessitates an increase in the effectiveness of urban wastewater purification. Therefore, this issue remains highly relevant [2]. The goal is to develop an efficient

water usage system for Tashkent and to improve the process of treating domestic and industrial wastewater generated in the city. To achieve this goal, the following tasks must be addressed:

- Study the types and composition of wastewater generated in the city;
- Analyze the wastewater discharge systems in the city;
- Evaluate the current methods used for wastewater treatment;
- Explore the theory behind treating wastewater containing various pollutants;
- Develop a mathematical model of the city's wastewater treatment process;
- Conduct experimental studies on urban wastewater treatment and analyze the results;
- Provide suggestions and recommendations for efficient water use in the city;
- Propose ideas and improvements for enhancing the city's wastewater treatment processes.

In accordance with the above objectives and tasks, microbiological analyses were conducted to assess the sanitary and hygienic conditions of urban wastewater samples. Additionally, research is underway to identify solutions for the treatment and reuse of wastewater and to develop biotechnological purification methods.

Biochemical treatment methods are used to remove dissolved organic and inorganic substances (such as hydrogen sulfide, sulfides, ammonia, and nitrites) from domestic and industrial wastewater. In this process, microorganisms utilize these substances as nutrients in their life activities—organic matter serves as a source of carbon for them [3,4].

Microorganisms partially decompose organic substances, converting them into water, carbon dioxide, nitrite, sulfate ions, and other compounds. The remaining portion of the organic substances is used to form **biomass** [5,6].

Only biological processes are used for the treatment of wastewater. In biological methods involving microorganisms, dissolved, colloidal, and suspended pollutants in the water are broken down. The number of bacteria participating in the purification process can reach 10^8 – 10^{14} **cells per gram** of dried sludge. The sludge has an extremely large surface area, with **100 m² of surface per gram** of mass. As a result, the rate of water purification increases. The size of the cells ranges from **0.1 to 3 mm**, and in some cases even exceeds 3 mm. Sludge and biofilms carry a **negative charge**, and their **pH ranges from 4 to 9** [7].

Therefore, it is crucial to first determine the **initial pollution level** of the water to be treated, especially by identifying the **microorganisms present** and their **main types**.

RESEARCH OBJECT AND METHODS

For the experiments, the following water samples were selected:

- Bozsuv canal water
- Sijjak iodized spring water
- Spring water produced at Bektemir Alcohol Plant
- Domestic water from Bektemir Alcohol Plant
- Luter water from Bektemir Alcohol Plant
- Heat-exchange water from Bektemir Alcohol Plant
- Inter Rohat water
- Water from Gafur Gulom Park

To determine whether these waters contained specific types of **microorganisms**, selective nutrient media characteristic of each microbial group were used:

- **Czapek-Dox** medium for fungi and actinomycetes

- **Nutrient agar** from HiMedia for general bacterial growth
- **Starch-ammonia** medium specifically for detecting actinomycetes

These nutrient media were prepared by combining organic compounds with mineral salts. For solid media, **2–3 grams of agar-agar** were added.

In this process, the following specific nutrient media were used: For bacteria: Peptone-agar (PA) medium, composed of the following per 100 ml: NaCl 0.5 g, Peptone – 1.0 g, agar 2.0 g, for fungi: Czapek-Dox medium, composition per liter: NaNO₃ – 2.0 g, KH₂PO₄ 1.0 g, KCl 0.5 g, MgSO₄ · 7H₂O – 0.5 g, FeSO₄ · 7H₂O 0.001 g, Sucrose – 30.0 g, agar 20.0 g, Distilled water – 1000 ml.

For actinomycetes: Starch-Ammonia agar (per liter): Starch – 20.0 g, FeSO₄ – 0.01 g, K₂HPO₄ – 0.5 g, MgSO₄ – 0.5 g, KNO₃ – 1.0 g, NaCl – 0.5 g, Water 1000 ml, agar 30.0 g, Ph adjusted to 7.2–7.4

For yeast and lactic acid bacteria: Beer wort medium (30% wort, 70 ml water, Ph 5.6–5.8) was used. Pathogenic rod-shaped bacteria were isolated using special peptone-based nutrient media.

The nutrient media, materials, and equipment required for the experiments were prepared in advance. From each collected sample, 0.1 ml was taken and poured into Petri dishes. Using sterile glass spreader rods, samples were inoculated using the lawn method. The inoculated Petri dishes were placed in an incubator (thermostat) set at 28–30°C and monitored over 2 to 5 days.

RESEARCH RESULTS AND THEIR ANALYSIS

As the object of scientific study, household and wastewater samples collected from various districts of Tashkent city and Tashkent region were cultivated on selective nutrient media. Microbial growth began to appear from the 48th hour of observation, and by days 5–7, a significant increase in the number of microbial colonies was recorded. Isolation of microbial strains was carried out based on the obtained cultures.

In particular, the microbiological state of the "Inter Rohat" water samples began to manifest as early as 24 hours, showing numerous bacterial colonies on the peptone nutrient medium.

Similarly, large quantities of bacteria were observed in the following samples:

- Sijjak Iodine Spring Water
- Swimming pool water from Gafur Gulom Park
- Bozsuv Canal water from Tashkent city

(See Figure — this refers to the image mentioned in the original text.)

General Microflora of Experimental Water Samples.			
The highest bacterial presence on Peptone-Agar (PA) nutrient medium: <i>Shigella</i> species observed			
Pepton-agar- Inter Rohat water	PA: Sijjak iodine spring water	PA: Bozsuv canal water	PA: Gafur Gulom garden water

PA: Bektemir alcohol plant heat exchange water	PA: Bektemir alcohol plant domestic (or household) water”	PA: Bektemir alcohol plant spring water”	Shigella: Sijjak iodine spring water
Shigella: Bektemir alcohol plant heat exchange water	Shigella: Bozsuv canal water	Shigella: Gafur Gulom garden water	Shigella: Bektemir lyuter water from the alcohol (spirits) factory
Shigella: Bektemir domestic (or household) water from the alcohol factory.	Shigella: Bektemir spring water from the alcohol factory	*Suslo: Bektemir Spring water of the alcohol factory”	Suslo: Bektemir domestic water of the alcohol factory
“General appearance of fungi and actinomycetes on beer wort agar and Chapek media.”			
Wort agar: Bozsuv Canal water	Wort: Sijjak Iodine Spring water	Wort: Gafur Gulom Park water	Wort: Bektemir Distillery Luther water

Wort agar: Bektemir Distillery heat exchange water	Actinomycetes: Sijjak Iodine Spring water	Actinomycetes: G'afur G'ulom Park water	Actinomycetes: Bo'zsuv Canal water
Actinomycetes: Bektemir Distillery heat exchange water	Actinomycetes: Bektemir Distillery domestic water	Actinomycetes: Bektemir Distillery domestic water	Actinomycetes: Bektemir Distillery "spring water"
Chapek: G'afur G'ulom Park water	Chapek: Bektemir Distillery domestic water	Chapek: Sijjak iodine spring water	Chapek: Bektemir Distillery heat exchange water
Chapek: Bektemir Distillery Lyuter water	Chapek: Bektemir Distillery "spring water"	Chapek: Bozsuv canal water	

Figure: Selective nutrient media: General view of microorganisms detected on PA (peptone-agar), Wort-agar (Suslo-agar), and Czapek-agar media.

Growth and Colony Formation of Microorganisms on Selective Nutrient Media
Determining the Microbiological-Sanitary and Pollution Levels of Water Samples

During a 120-hour observation period of conducted experiments, nearly all water samples including those from the Bozsuv River, Sijjak Iodine Spring, production spring water from Bektemir distillery, household wastewater from the distillery, heat-exchange water, "Inter Rohat" water, and Gafur Gulom Park pond were found to contain bacteria, fungi, actinomycetes, and certain pathogenic microorganisms. Preliminary results revealed that all water samples contained major groups of microorganisms, and that the quantity and type of these organisms depended on the water source. Notably, even the production spring water from Bektemir distillery showed a significant presence of bacteria and fungi. Therefore, the study clearly indicates an urgent need to develop treatment methods, particularly to eliminate pathogenic microorganisms from these waters.

CONCLUSION

It is known that bacteria, fungi, and algae are considered active agents in the biological treatment of industrial wastewater. When water becomes overly saturated with various pollutants, different standalone or combined treatment methods are used for purification. To establish a closed-loop water supply system, industrial wastewater is treated depending on the type of enterprise — using mechanical, chemical, physicochemical, biological, and thermal methods, until the desired water quality is achieved.

In addition, these treatment methods are classified into recovery (recuparation) and destructive types:

- Recovery methods aim to extract and reuse valuable substances found in wastewater.
- Destructive methods involve the oxidation or reduction of pollutants to break them down and eliminate them.
- Currently, research and experiments are ongoing to thoroughly study the microorganisms present in water, identify their genera and species, and develop combined approaches using physical and biotechnological methods for their removal and purification.

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